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Graphwise.ai

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Semantic Problems in Dataspaces

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Graphical Abstract

An allegorical representation of DCAT as Atlas who underpins the sharing of datasets worldwide; but in a crippled state with missing parts, due to its diminished adoption by the Eclipse Dataspace Components, symbolized as a sword labeled "EDC".

Anyone can be a Picasso by using LLMs

Outline

Ontologies and Dataspace Metadata

- Semantic interoperability of dataspace
- Data Catalog (DCAT) ontology
- UNDERPIN project

EDC Metadata Problems

- Improper content type and context
- Wrong namespaces
- No base; bad instance URIs
- Disconnected RDF
- Doesn't conform to ODRL

Github Discussions

- "There is no conformance test yet"
- TCK doesn't use W3C test approaches
- Emphasis on JSON not JSON-LD
- "Sidestep the black hole of semantic data"

Dataspace Implementation Problems

- Doesn't use semtech in implementation
- Cannot be extended easily with other semantic metadata

Other Dataspace Semantic Problems

- Sovity
- IDSA
- GAIA-X

The background features a light blue and white color palette. A grid of small, light blue dots is arranged in a pattern that is partially obscured by a large, white, curved shape on the right side. On the left side, there are several abstract shapes, including a small blue circle and a larger white circle, both with soft shadows.

Ontologies and Dataspace Metadata

Semantic interop of dataspace

Semantic interoperability is a hot topic:

- Workshop [Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces](#) organized 3 years in a row by SWC, W3C, ERCIM, IDSA and BDVA
- Workshop [Semantics in DataSpaces at WWW 2023](#) and at [ESWC 2024](#) organized by RWTH Aachen
- Workshop by [GO-FAIR and IDSA](#).
- [Dataspace Community Group](#) was established at W3C in May 2024. Was hot topic at the premier EU data sharing event EBDVF, with [6 sessions in EBDVF 2024](#).

Interoperability is important:

- Great value for dataspace consumers: harmonization of dataset form and meaning
- Precondition to dataspace federation: makes little sense to federate data without harmonization

Interoperability is elusive

- Previously [1] [2] [3] we wrote about the need for semantic harmonization of **business (payload) data**
- But it turns out that semantic **metadata** in dataspace also has numerous problems

Data Catalog (DCAT) ontology

[Dataset Catalog \(DCAT\) ontology](#) is well established:

- Mature: has been in development since 2014
- Foundation of numerous data sharing initiatives, including [European Data Portal](#).
- Various DCAT profiles
 - EU datasets (DCAT-AP),
 - statistics ([StatDCAT-AP](#)),
 - geospatial ([GeoDCAT-AP](#)),
 - life sciences ([HCLS Dataset](#) [4]),
 - national (DE, NO, DK, SE, IT), etc.
- DCAT is the underpinning of the IDSA [Dataspaces Protocol](#) (DSP)
 - [Catalog and Dataset responses](#).

DSP also uses the [Open Digital Rights Language](#) (ODRL) to express access and usage rights over datasets.

UNDERPIN project

UNDERPIN is funded by the Digital Europe call "Manufacturing Dataspaces".

A dataspace of maintenance sensor data and predictive analytics.

Energy domain: refinery, wind farms.

Reuses many ontologies to describe:

- DCAT: datasets
- CSVW: dataset columns
- QUDT: quantity kinds and units of measure
- PROV: dataset links
- SSN/SOSA: features of interest of columns/sensors

[Semantic model](#) is an open project

- [UNDERPIN Semantic Model](#)
 - [Contents](#)
 - [Glossary](#)
 - [Preliminary Materials](#)
- [Reference Ontologies](#)
 - [Dataspace Protocol](#)
 - [DCAT](#)
 - [CSVW](#)
 - [QUDT](#)
 - [QB](#)
 - [SDMX for Common Properties](#)
 - [Statistical Qualifiers](#)
 - [PROV](#)
 - [SSN/SOSA](#)
 - [Wind Turbine Ontologies](#)
- [UNDERPIN Data Organization](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Semantic Data Loading](#)
- [UNDERPIN Data Model](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Prefixes](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Thesauri](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Statistical Qualifiers](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Units and Quantity Kinds](#)
 - [UNDERPIN Features of Interest](#)
 - [Dataset Model](#)
 - [Dataset After Ingestion](#)
 - [Dataset Relations](#)
 - [Table Schema Model](#)
 - [Using LLM for Column Descriptions](#)
- [UNDERPIN Semantic Search](#)
 - [Semantic Search UI](#)

UNDERPIN semantic model

- Dataset (DCAT: left), table schema (CSVW: right), dataset relations (DCAT & PROV: bottom)
- Very little of this fits in DSP metadata, so we use GraphDB to store and workarounds to integrate

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EDC Implementation Problems

Doesn't use semtech in implementation

GRAPHWISE
AI THRIVES ON WHOLE DATA

Eclipse Dataspace Components:

- A popular dataspace implementation, used by Catena-X, Mobility Dataspace, etc
- In the UNDERPIN we use EDC/Sovity, based on EDC version 0.2.1 (a year old).
The reported problems occur in this version
- Latest released version is EDC [0.10.1](#) (2 months old): some problems are fixed, but not all.

EDC does not use semantic technologies in its implementation:

- Dataset metadata is stored in Postgres ("on persistence ... we don't store anything related to DCAT")
- Doesn't use an Object-RDF Mapping (ORM) framework; limited ontology classes are implemented as Java POJO classes by hand, ontology terms are hard-coded in the Java implementation.
- JSON-LD is stored in **edc:assetJsonLd** (text field, CLOB), not following semantic principles
- Custom props are allowed (**edc:properties**), but it doesn't follow semantic extensibility principles.
Problems, eg [sovity/edc-ce/discussions/1103](#) "how to use our own JSONLD in a custom field?"

This leads to some errors (eg namespaces), and more difficult maintenance and extension efforts.

Cannot be extended easily

As a consequence, EDC cannot be extended easily with new semantic metadata

- Supports only a restricted version of DCAT, e.g. a Dataset can have only 1 Distribution.
- Captures/indexes only a few DCAT fields
- Does not facilitate easy extensibility with additional classes (e.g. **dcat:DatasetSeries**), fields, relations (eg **prov:wasDerivedFrom**) or whole new domain areas (e.g. **CSVW** for column-level metadata).
- Extensibility through **edc:properties** or **edc:assetJsonLd** does not conform to semantic web's Open World Assumption, where we can add extra classes and properties directly on the nodes to be extended.

Needed for UNDERPIN:

- Column-level descriptions using CSVW ontology, SOSA for features, QUDT for units/quantities
- Temporal slices (monthly, weekly or daily) from the same sensors. Represent slices (CSV) as **dcat:Dataset** and link them using **dcat:inSeries** to **dcat:DatasetSeries** (Influx) that grows in time.
- **prov:wasBasedOn** relation from predictive analytics result to input dataset

EDC Metadata Problems

Improper content type and context

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[underpin-project/dcat#dataspace-catalog-response](#) and following sections:

- Catalog metadata: returns **application/json** instead of **application/ld+json**
- Doesn't import the "canonical" DSP context <https://w3id.org/dspace/2024/1/context.json>,
 - See first line of the diagram in [Dataspace Protocol Catalog Response](#), and the example [catalog.json](#)
- Instead uses a deficient and defective inline context:
 - Uses wrong namespaces
 - Doesn't define property types. In particular, lacking **"type": "@id"** results in disconnected RDF graph

It's obvious nobody has tried to convert EDC metadata to an RDF semantic graph

Wrong namespaces

- Wrong namespace **dcat**: <https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat/> (http not https, trailing hash not slash)
 - Fixed 11 months ago in [eclipse-edc/Connector/pull/3781](https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/pull/3781) "align DCAT namespace IRI to the correct one"
- **dct:endpointUrl** is non-existent, should be **dcat:endpointURL**.
 - Partially fixed 8 months ago in [eclipse-edc/pull/4146](https://github.com/eclipse-edc/pull/4146) (from **dct:endpointUrl** to **dcat:endpointUrl**)
 - Later fixed 3 months ago in [eclipse-edc/pull/4524](https://github.com/eclipse-edc/pull/4524) (from **dcat:endpointUrl** to **dcat:endpointURL**),
 - Wrong property remains as "deprecated" because existing EDC deployments may still use it
 - Multiple files had to be corrected; one-off fixing doesn't guarantee correctness
- Wrong namespace **dct**: <https://purl.org/dc/terms/> (http not https)
- Obsolete namespace **dspace**: <https://w3id.org/dspace/v0.8/>, correct one is <https://w3id.org/dspace/2024/1/> (from "canonical" DSP context)
- Uses both prefixed URLs with wrong prefix, and full URLs, eg:
 - **dcat:Dataset**, **dcat:service** use wrong prefix, <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword> is a correct URL but unshortened
 - **dct:terms** uses wrong prefix, <http://purl.org/dc/terms/license> is a correct URL but unshortened
- Namespace **edc**: <https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/> doesn't resolve
 - Metadata uses such properties, which are therefore undefined

No base; bad instance URIs

- Doesn't specify **@base**
 - Thus all **@id** fields are incorrectly resolved to local file URLs (depending on RDFization tool).
 - Eg <file:///D:/Onto/proj/underpin/model/dcat/5e839777-d93e-4785-8972-1005f51cf367> (the wrong part is underlined)
- Uses bad instance URIs for **odrl:Set** based on some hash, including colons
 - Eg OGU0ZTMzMGMtODQ2ZS00ZWmxLThmOGQtNWQxNWM0NmI2NmY4:YmNjYTYxYmUtZTgyZS00ZGE2L...
 - Error "11/LOWERCASE_PREFERRED in SCHEME: lowercase is preferred in this component" from Jena riot.
 - The error means that the very long part before : is taken to be a URI scheme (completely wrong)

Disconnected RDF

Red shows errors

One of the most serious errors:

- some relations (things)
- are misrepresented as attributes (strings)

Doesn't conform to ODRL

- [Open Digital Rights Language](#) (ODRL) is used by DSP to express access and usage rights over datasets
- EDC uses nested node `{"odrl:action": {"odrl:type": ...}}`, doesn't conform to ODRL:
 - [ODRL Information Model 2.2](#) doesn't define **odrl:type**
 - [odrl.jsonld](#) context doesn't define such term.
 - None of the "action" examples show a "type" subnode
- Uses a plain string "USE" as value. But:
 - [IDSA Contract JSON schema](#) uses prefixed URLs, and one of the allowed values is **"odrl:use"**
 - [odrl.jsonld](#) context specifies it's a URL:
`"action": {"@type": "@vocab", "@id": "odrl:action"}`
(**@vocab** means that by default it's resolved in the vocabulary namespace)

Other Dataspace Semantic Problems

Is the problem only with EDC?

Found some problems in the wider dataspace context.

- Sevity:
 - [soivity/edc-ce/discussions/1103](https://soivity.edc-ce/discussions/1103) "how to use our own JSONLD in a custom field?" describes problems related to extending an EDC payload with your own properties.
- IDSA: problems in protocol, context, shapes (not answered yet):
 - ids-specification/issues/276 problem with odr!target shape
 - ids-specification/issues/278 Return content type **application/json** vs **application/ld+json**
 - ids-specification/issues/277 context should define more props as @id
- GAIA-X: gaia-x.eu/trusted-shape-registry/shapestrustframework uses recursive shapes:

```
@id: "gx:LegalParticipantShape",  
sh:property: [  
  sh:path: {@id: "gx:parentOrganization"},  
  sh:node: {@id: "gx:LegalParticipantShape"}]
```

 - Recursive shapes are undefined in SHACL 1.0.
 - Might be added in a future SHACL version
 - in any case it's not a good idea to overuse **sh:node** because this leads to uncontrollable expansion of validation work.
- SIMPL? Huge project (150+15 MEUR), but I'm not aware of any specific semantic effort

Github Discussions

Excuse: TCK is in development

Quotes from EDC founder and developers:

- **No implementation can "conform"** to Dataspace Protocol (DSP) because a TCK has not been published at Eclipse. This is a work in progress and EDC does intend to pass the TCK when it is available. There will continue to be mismatches as the specifications are a work-in-progress.
- Alignment will be done in conjunction with the effort to pass the DSP TCK (Technology Compatibility Kit at eclipse-dataspacetck/dsp-tck/). This work will be undertaken by the committers to ensure backward compatibility with the current **protocol support, if possible**.
- We are aware of these and a number of other mismatches with the DSP specification. There will continue to be mismatches as the **specifications are a work-in-progress**. (a) Both DSP and the EDC are moving targets, so expect divergence; (b) The EDC committers are well aware of this divergence, but thanks for bringing it to our attention; and (c) this divergence will be addressed by the ongoing DSP TCK efforts.
- We are **not using Json-LD for semantic/RDF purposes**. DSP is moving heavily to a Json-Schema approach. This will entail profiling (restricting) both DCAT and ODRL in favor of interoperability, and in particular, removing the requirement to process DSP messages as Json-Ld. The DSP specification will promote interoperability between DSP implementations. The message types will be defined using **Json-Schema**. Interoperability will be guaranteed by a TCK that is already underway.

This misses some important points

- DSP steps on a number of **established semantic technologies** (JSON-LD) and ontologies (DCAT and ODRL). No matter how much DSP evolves, **implementations of the DSP must comply** with these and cannot use **strings instead of URLs, undefined URLs, unsuitable strings as URL** values, **mismatching namespaces, wrong properties**, etc.
- To misspell namespaces and properties in **multiple Java source files**, and then to keep them around with status "deprecated" for the purposes of **backward compatibility** with **non-conforming** implementations, is not to best way to promote interoperability and maintainability.
- There are a number of established **semantic validation technologies**, in particular SHACL and SHEX validation, describing tests semantically using the **W3C Test Manifest** and results using **EARL** ontologies. A brief inspection of the TCK does not show that any of these approaches are being used.
- Before any **W3C spec** can attain Recommendation status, it must have a **conformance test** suite expressed in machine-readable form using Test Manifest; and EARL reports from **at least 2 implementations**, which machine-readable artefacts are the underpinning of W3C Implementation Reports. These positive W3C practices seem to have been **ignored in EDC** development.

JSON not JSON-LD

- "We are **not using Json-LD** for semantic/RDF purposes. The DSP specification will promote interoperability between DSP **implementations**. The message types will be defined using **Json-Schema**. This approach is consistent with the one adopted by the VC Data Model 2.0 specification. DSP and EDC payloads are valid Json-Ld."
- I completely agree with a dual approach: JSON **and** JSON-LD. The big difference is whether
 - JSON payloads are also valid JSON-LD
 - Instances conform to basic web architecture principles (e.g. valid URLs that refer to other nodes),
 - They follow certain ontologies and SHACL shapes.
- If JSON-LD is valid then semantic technologies can be used for complex analytics and queries.
 - E.g. SPARQL is very useful for complex data such as AAS.
- From the problems described above it is very clear that nobody has tried to convert EDC metadata from JSON to semantic form.
 - The bugs are so many that the graph is unusable on its own, let alone if you try to use it in conjunction with other ontologies and KGs.

Conclusion

A wake-up call

- "The EDC is specifically designed to **sidestep the black hole of semantic data** by simply storing asset properties in expanded form... **in favor of interoperability**"
- I find it ironic that EDC finds it easier to address **interoperability** by specifically sidestepping semantic approaches.
- This is a serious **wake-up call** to the dataspace community: do not ignore decades of **semantic interoperability experience!**
- It is an even more serious call to the semantic community: despite major commercial interest in **Knowledge Graphs** in the last 2-4 years, **dataspaces** remain outside of the semantic approach

References

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